

POLISILINDIRIK SOHA

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Annotatsiya: Z_k ($k=1,2,\dots,n$) kompleks tekisligida Koshi tipidagi integralning umumiy ko'rinishi haqida.

Аннотация: Об общем виде интеграла типа Коши в комплексной плоскости Z_k ($k=1,2,\dots,n$).

Annotation: About the general appearance of the Koshi type integral in the complex plane Z_k ($k=1,2,\dots,n$).

Z_k ($k=1,2,\dots,n$) kompleks tekisligida γ^k - to'g'irlanuvchi yopiq Jordan chizig'i berilgan bo'lib, uning uzunligi l_k , diametri esa d_k bo'lsin. Chegarasi γ^k bo'lgan sohani ichki soha va uni D_k^+ bilan, $D_k^+ \cup \gamma^k$ sohani butun kompleks sohaga to'ldiruvchi sohani tashqi va uni D_k^- bilan belgilaymiz.

γ^k ($k=1,2,\dots,n$) yopiq chiziqlarning berilishi butun n kompleks tekisligini 2^n ta turli polisilindirik sohaga ajratadi va ularni $D_1^\pm \times D_2^\pm \times \dots \times D_n^\pm$ deb belgilaymiz. Ularning ichidagi ushbu C_n^1 ta: $D_1^+ \times D_2^+ \times \dots \times D_n^+$ ($D_1^- \times D_2^- \times \dots \times D_n^-$) sohani $D^+(D^-)$ bilan; $D_1^+ \times D_2^+ \times \dots \times D_{p-1}^+ \times D_p^- \times D_{p+1}^+ \times \dots \times D_n^+$ ($D_1^- \times D_2^- \times \dots \times D_{p-1}^- \times D_p^+ \times D_{p+1}^- \times \dots \times D_n^-$) sohani D_{-p}^+ (D_{+p}^-) bilan; C_n^2 ta: $D_1^+ \times D_2^+ \times \dots \times D_{p-1}^+ \times D_p^- \times D_{p+1}^+ \times \dots \times D_{q-1}^- \times D_q^- \times D_{q+1}^+ \times \dots \times D_n^+$ ($D_1^- \times D_2^- \times \dots \times D_{p-1}^- \times D_p^+ \times D_{p+1}^- \times \dots \times D_{q-1}^- \times D_q^+ \times D_{q+1}^- \times \dots \times D_n^-$) sohani D_{-pq}^+ (D_{+pq}^-) ($p,q=1,2,\dots,n$; $p < q$) bilan belgilaymiz va hokazo.

Bu polisilindirik sohalarning hammasining chegarasining umumiy qismi, ya'ni $\gamma^1 \times \gamma^2 \times \dots \times \gamma^n$ ni ostov deb ataymiz va uni $\Delta = \gamma^1 \times \gamma^2 \times \dots \times \gamma^n$ kabi belgilaymiz.

1-ta'rif. Agar $\Phi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)$ funksiya D^+ sohada aniqlangan bo'lib, $\forall (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n) \in \Delta$ uchun $\exists \lim_{D^+ \ni (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \rightarrow (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)} \Phi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lim_{D^+ \ni z \rightarrow t} \Phi(z) = \Phi^+(t)$ bo'lsa, u holda $\Phi(z)$ funksiya D^+ dan ostovga uzluksiz davom ettiriladi deyiladi. Bunda $z = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)$, $t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$.

Xuddi shunday funksiyaning D^- , $D_{-p}^+(D_{+p}^-)$, $D_{-pq}^+(D_{+pq}^-)$ sohalardan ostovgacha uzluksiz davom ettirish ta'riflari beriladi.

2-ta'rif. Agar $\Phi(z)$ funksiya $D^\pm$ sohalarning har biridan ostovgacha uzluksiz davom ettirilsa, u holda $\Phi(z)$ funksiya ostovgacha uzluksiz davom ettiriladi deyiladi.

Ushbu

$$\Phi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) = \frac{1}{(2\pi i)^n} \int_{\Delta} \frac{f(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)}{\prod_{k=1}^n (\tau_k - z_k)} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \dots d\tau_n \quad (1)$$

ko'rinishdagi n karrali Koshi tipidagi integralni qaraylik.

Bunda $f(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \in \Delta$

Yozishni qisqartirish maqsadida quydagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$\tau = (\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n), \quad t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$$

$$\tau_{t_p} = (\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{p-1}, t_p, \tau_{p+1}, \dots, \tau_n)$$

$$t_{\tau_p} = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{p-1}, \tau_p, t_{p+1}, \dots, t_n)$$

$$\tau_{t_{pq}} = (\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{p-1}, t_p, \tau_{p+1}, \dots, \tau_{q-1}, t_q, \tau_{q+1}, \dots, \tau_n)$$

$(p, q = 1, 2, \dots, n; p < q)$ va hokazo.

$$N = (1, 2, \dots, n), \quad N_{[p]} = (1, 2, \dots, p-1, p+1, \dots, n),$$

$$N_{[pq]} = (1, 2, \dots, p-1, p+1, \dots, q-1, q+1, \dots, n)$$

va hokazo.

$$t_{[p]} = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{p-1}, t_{p+1}, \dots, t_n)$$

$$t_{[pq]} = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{p-1}, t_{p+1}, \dots, t_{q-1}, t_{q+1}, \dots, t_n), \quad (p, q = 1, 2, \dots, n; p < q)$$

va hokazo.

$$d\tau = d\tau_1 \cdot d\tau_2 \cdot \dots \cdot d\tau_n, \quad dt_{[p]} = dt_1 \cdot dt_2 \cdot \dots \cdot dt_{p-1} \cdot dt_{p+1} \cdot \dots \cdot dt_n,$$

$$dt_{[pq]} = d\tau_1 \cdot d\tau_2 \cdot \dots \cdot d\tau_{p-1} \cdot d\tau_{p+1} \cdot \dots \cdot d\tau_{q-1} \cdot d\tau_{q+1} \cdot \dots \cdot d\tau_{q-1} \cdot d\tau_{q+1} \cdot \dots \cdot d\tau_n$$

va hokazo.

$$\Delta_{[p]} = \gamma^1 \times \gamma^2 \times \dots \times \gamma^{p-1} \times \gamma^{p+1} \times \dots \times \gamma^n,$$

$$\Delta_{[pq]} = \gamma^1 \times \gamma^2 \times \dots \times \gamma^{p-1} \times \gamma^{p+1} \times \dots \times \gamma^{q-1} \times \gamma^{q+1} \times \dots \times \gamma^n,$$

va hokazo.

$$\eta^2 = \eta_1^2 \cdot \eta_2^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \eta_n^2, \quad \eta_{[p]}^2 = \eta_1^2 \cdot \eta_2^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \eta_{p-1}^2 \cdot \eta_{p+1}^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \eta_n^2$$

$$\eta_{[pq]}^2 = \eta_1^2 \cdot \eta_2^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \eta_{p-1}^2 \cdot \eta_{p+1}^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \eta_{q-1}^2 \cdot \eta_{q+1}^2 \cdot \eta_n^2 \quad \text{va hokazo.}$$

$$\tau - z = \prod_{k=1}^n (\tau_k - z_k), \quad (\tau - z)_{[p]} = \prod_{k=1}^n (\tau_k - z_k), \quad (k \neq p, p = \overline{1, n})$$

$$(\tau - z)_{[pq]} = \prod_{k=1}^n (\tau_k - z_k), \quad (k \neq p, q; p < q; p, q = \overline{1, n})$$

va hokazo.

Yuqoridagi belgilashlarni e'tiborga olgan holda (1) Koshi tipidagi integral ushbu

$$\Phi(z) = \frac{1}{(2\pi i)^n} \int_{\Delta} \frac{f(\tau)}{\tau - z} d\tau \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishga keladi.

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